

Framing Ubuntu Philosophy to Reconstruct Principals' Behaviour and Teachers' effectiveness in Secondary Schools

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Abstract

The dwindling of teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools as linked to the behaviour of principals necessitates this study. The study was theorised with Ubuntu philosophy to uncover deficiencies relating to principals' organisational behaviour indices such as; communication, participatory decision making and stress management as correlates of teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State

Nigeria. Descriptive research of survey design was used to cover all public secondary schools in Ekiti State. Seven hundred and twenty (720) respondents were sampled; 360 teachers and 360 students were selected using a multi-stage sampling procedure. Principal Behaviours Questionnaire" (PBQ) administered on teachers and "Teacher Effectiveness Questionnaire" (TEQ) administered on students were used to collect data. Face and content validity were used to ascertain the degree of accuracy and appropriateness of the instruments. Test-retest reliability method of the instruments was done with reliability coefficients of 0.77 and 0.94 respectively. Descriptive statistics (frequency counts and percentages) and Inferential Statistics (Pearson Product Moment Correlation PPMC and Regression Analysis) were used to analyse the data. The study found out that the effectiveness of teachers is on average while principals' behaviour variables are highly significant to teachers' effectiveness with the conclusion that communication, participatory decision making and principal stress management are the dimension of teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools.

Key words: Ubuntu philosophy, Principals' behaviour, Teachers' effectiveness, Secondary schools.

Introduction

Secondary education all over the world prepares learners not only for academic excellence and higher education but also inculcate into learners the need for self-awareness, personal and societal development (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013; Republic of Ghana, 2013). This implies that secondary education contributes in no small measure to both the learners' and the national development of any given nation. Nigeria is not an exception. Secondary school education in Nigeria runs for six years, and it is divided into two stages; which according to Ige (2012) are junior secondary schools and senior secondary schools with three years duration for each of the

levels. This level of education, according to Garba (2012) builds on primary education and lays the foundations for university education, life orientation, and human development by offering subjects on skill-oriented education. Apart from this, this level of education equips learners with talent discovery to live effectively in the age of modern technology; it also projects Nigerian culture such as the art and languages; develop learners for critical thinking and problem solving skills; respect for people's views and feelings; it equally foster unity in diversity and good citizenry (FGN, 2004; 2013).

In order to achieve the national policy statements, the role of teachers and the schools administrators such as principal cannot be underrated because teachers and principals alongside their activities have been equated to the hub and drive for effective curriculum implementation in the system (Ekundayo, Omodan & Omodan, 2018; Omodan, Ekundayo & Bamikole, 2018). That is, the effective and efficient achievement of secondary school goals and objectives depend on the teachers and their readiness to take the bull by the horns. In doing this, the principals' behaviours which could be measured by their dispositions to organisational situations and management such as communication, decision making, and stress management among others are as important as the school itself (Babalola, 2019). This is to say, that the indices of principals' behaviour include but not limited to their ability to manage communication, decision-making processes and their dispositions toward controlling or managing teachers' stress.

Hence, for teachers to be effective in discharging their duties, the role and behaviours of the principals in managing its human capital such as teachers cannot be quantified. This is in line with the findings of Ekundayo *et al.* (2018) that there is a significant relationship between teachers' effectiveness and principals' activities. That is, teachers are likely to be productive when there are positive behaviours from their administrators. In this study, teachers' effectiveness is measured by the teachers' attributes. This, according to Aina, Olanipekun and Garuba (2015) are teachers' interaction with learners, teachers' teaching strategies, motivation, classroom management, pedagogical and content knowledge of the guiding curriculum. Likewise, teachers' effectiveness is linked to the teacher's ability to select appropriate teaching and learning mechanisms to enhance the teaching-learning process in order to bring about positive learning outcomes (Oviawe, 2016). From these perspectives, one could conclude that an effective teacher is the one whose inputs have generated good outcomes such as improvement on students' academic achievement.

As beneficial as teachers' effectiveness is to learners, research has shown that teachers are not as productive as expected in secondary schools. This was reflected in students' academic performance in both internal and external examinations in Ekiti State Nigeria (Kayode & Ayodele, 2015; Omodan et al., 2018). Observations showed that teachers are demotivated mostly by the way the schools are been administered by the administrators. Teachers at various times complained about the gaps in communication and principal lackadaisical attitudes to upwards communications. It was also observed that most principals hardly involve teachers in the decision-making process in the school; this in our conclusion, makes teachers feel irrelevant in the running of the school system. Among other practices observed by the researchers is the principals' disposition towards managing organisational stress relating to teachers. No wonder that communication, decision making, and stress management were founded as indicators of proper behaviour in schools (Kolawole, 2016; Babalola, 2019). Therefore, since these indices are regarded as necessary in managing secondary schools, then, these deficiencies may not be unconnected to principals' behaviours such as communication, decision making, and principals' management of stress-related to teachers.

Communication and Teachers' Effectiveness

Communication is seen as a central factor for the effectiveness of staff in any organisation including secondary schools. According to Olaleye (2007), communication is a process of information exchange between two or more individuals in organisations (Habaci, 2013). In schools organisation, information is being transmitted from administrators to teachers, from teachers to pupils, from pupils to pupils, from pupils to teachers and lots more. Even the process of teaching and learning is also regarded as a process of communication. Findings from various researchers revealed that ability of school managers to communicate effectively would increase teachers' morale to work effectively and reduce misunderstanding and interpersonal conflict among staff which will, therefore, enhance teacher effectiveness (Gray, 2013; Rai, 2018). This is to confirm further that the principal's role in maintaining good effectiveness among teachers lies in professional and personal relationships which could only be ensured through good communication system (Weber & Scott, 2013). This is to say that a successful principalship requires good organisational communication skills in order to enhance understanding among stakeholders (Teachers and Principal). This will create between teachers and principals less of a gap and no misperceptions (Rai, 2018).

The perceived ineffectiveness of teachers in secondary schools seems to be as a result of poor interpersonal relations such as written and unwritten means of communication from the school head to the teachers. Effective disposition of information is supposed to be a panacea to solving individual and group problems alongside the development of the school itself. The reverse is the case in secondary schools in Ekiti State as it was observed that there is staff dissatisfaction over communication gaps between the school principals and the subordinates (teachers), where mostly the teachers feel left out or left in solitary confinement from the operations of the schools. This level of teachers' dissatisfaction as observed by Ayamolowo, Irinoye & Oladoyin (2013) was linked to a lack of good communication system in schools. Consequently, the above paucity will negatively affect performance leading to teachers' ineffectiveness, of which the aftermath is detrimental to the general productivity of secondary schools if not checked.

Decision making and Teachers' Effectiveness

Decision making, according to Fakunle (2017), involves mapping the likely consequences of decisions, working out the importance of individual factors, and choosing the best course of action to take. Teachers' participation in decision-making in matters that affect them is highly desirable. Nwobosi (1983) in his study pointed out that any organisation that failed to make effective use of the creative abilities of its employees should expect the display of negative initiatives and imagination which would contradict the goals and objectives of such an organisation. In secondary schools, such actions could lead to teachers' ineffectiveness. The researcher's interaction with some secondary school teachers revealed that decision-making problems exist in the schools, according to the teachers, the superior take a certain decision without involving the subordinates. This observation is in line with the findings of Peretomode (2012) which revealed that most secondary schools in Warri Metropolis do not involve their teachers in decision-making as the teachers have desired. In other words, the principals appear to adopt an autocratic approach to the decision-making process. In contention to this, the findings of Uchendu, Anijaobi-Idem & Nkama (2013) showed that teachers who had opportunity to always and actively participate in decision-making processes of the school were more enthusiastic about their job than those who had limited opportunities to participate. This is an indication that when teachers are not involved in the decision-making process may lead to negative teachers' behaviours, which may eventually affect their effectiveness.

Inference from the above observation and findings become a point of concern because the lack of teachers' participation in decision making will negatively affect the attitudes of teachers toward their work and their level of effectiveness. Even the decision-making process in schools does not only affect teachers' productivity but could also be the reason attributed to the negative impact of policies and organizational rules which are meant to guide teachers on their job activities (Kolawole, 2016). The above assumption is not in line with what is obtainable in the secondary schools as observations show that decisions concerning teachers and other staffs are taken without their involvement, maybe because of a general perception that a judge cannot be a judge in his case or probably as a result of imperfection on the part of the school head toward understanding the intricate of leadership. Therefore, by allowing a diverse group of employees to have input into decisions most especially the one that concerns them, the organisation tends to benefit from the collaboration that comes from a wider choice of options. When all teachers, non-teaching staff and school heads are allowed to participate, the chances to the increased unique and productive idea will be suggested and agreed upon.

Principal's Management of Teachers' Stress and Teachers' Effectiveness

Stress in an organisation is seen as lack of harmonious interface between teachers and their work environment. Olaleye (2007) opined that stress can be an unhealthy stimulus to creative acts or burden with harmful effects. Stress is a major challenge to workers' health and the healthiness of their organisations (International Labour Organisation, 2001). In secondary schools, teachers who are stressed are most likely to be unhealthy, less productive and less effective in discharging their duties also their schools are likely to experience ill success in productivity. Meanwhile, organisations may find it difficult to protect their workers from stress arising outside of work, but they can protect them from stress that arises within the work situation (Kolawole, 2016). Among other things that caused internal stress are found to be prevalent in schools are lack of teaching and learning materials, environmental pressures, pressure to produce better exam results, pressure to perform extraneous tasks, and extreme classroom ecology (Pagayanan, 2016). The findings of Bongo and Casta (2017) verified the prevalence of work stress among teachers therefore can no longer be denied among educators nowadays with recommendation that it must be prevented. By doing this, school administrators must be aware of it and know how to help in order to get the best out of the teachers. That is, the principal needs to know how to manage the stress of teachers in

the school system because the behaviour of principals towards stress management may influence positively the effectiveness of teachers.

The effects of stress in secondary schools in Ekiti State is evident in the observed increase in lateness to work, increase in the request for sick leaves and consequently low productivity. This is not only observed by the researchers but scholars like; Kavita & Hassan (2018) and Ukonu, Serieke-Dickson & Edeoga (2019) had found out that teachers stress was a major contributor to their ineffective. Despite the obvious negative effects of stress on the teachers' job effectiveness, many principals in secondary schools in Ekiti State, have not deemed it fit to put in place any workable measures to address this perpetual problem. This conclusion was made based on the observation made by the researchers about the current overcrowded classrooms, pressure from parents, limited resources in secondary schools teachers in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Even the potential of physical violence is not exempted, and management of these schools does not seem to have provided institutional support for staff suffering from stress.

In summary, it is evidenced from the above exploration to conclude that communication, participation in decision making and stress management as the attributes of principals' behaviours is vital in ensuring effective teachers' and general productivity in secondary schools. Moreover, if not managed appropriately may lead otherwise. Therefore, principals' willingness to work effectively with teachers will likely increase teachers' morale for effectiveness and consequently enhance the achievement of goal and objectives of secondary schools. However, the study will respond to the above-observed teacher's ineffectiveness by framing the highlighted problems with Ubuntu philosophy to ensure that all stakeholders in secondary schools are unitedly related to work towards the goals of the system.

Theoretical Framework: Situating the Study in Ubuntu Philosophy

In order to address the teachers and principal relationship in terms of their behaviours towards work, Ubuntu is framed to respond to the gaps. Ubuntu from an etymological point of view was derived from the Xhosa language words; "ubu" which mean "being" and "ntu" which mean "human" (Ramose, 1999). That is Ubuntu could be referred to as "quality of being human" (Sparks, 1990; Tworeck, Hemminga, Huber & Dhillon, 2015). Ubuntu is also a philosophy that is predominated in humanity where people exist because there are people, meaning, a person is a person through others (Moloketi, 2009; Khomba, 2011). Ubuntu is a way of life conceptualized in Africa to mean selfless services for others, caring for others, protecting fellow human beings

(Msila, 2015). In the view of Brack, Hill, Edwards, Grootboom, and Lassiter (2003), Ubuntu is a philosophy of life that is fundamental to the morality, humanness, humanity and personhood that shapes people's social conduct. This means that Ubuntu is the factor of human sociality and perceptions that influence social conduct which is found to have contributed to the management of disparities among the people throughout Africa and beyond (Nzimakwe, 2014). With these, we could argue that Ubuntu has become an indigenous world view preaching the essence of humanity, love for one another through one another.

The concept of 'Ubuntu' is very important in managing human beings in any organizations, including secondary schools. The school community is made up of teachers, students, and administrators who must work hand in hand to make the school fulfil its goals and objectives. By doing this, the schools need the best leadership model and strategies for the principals and teachers to be able to discharge their duties effectively. Hence, one of the philosophy that could help the principal and other members of the schools to develop a good practice of doing things together, and in togetherness is Ubuntu (Mbigi, 1997, 2000, 2004). Not only that, its principles on interconnectedness among people is a pointer to teachers and principal's positive behaviours (Msila, 2008; Mbhele, 2015). Apart from this, the characteristic of Ubuntu as propounded by Msengana (2006) includes; relatedness, collectivism, communalism spirituality, social and interpersonal relationships are needed to maintain effectiveness in the school system. By practising this, it will promote quality leadership by ensuring principals commitment and development of social respect and responsibilities for ethical attitude towards others (Lefa, 2015). In the other way round, when there is the practice of Ubuntu in schools, the teachers who are bent on it is likely to be compassionate, dedicated to providing quality and caring teaching styles to learners thereby resulting in students learning outcomes which could make the teacher to be regarded as being effective.

This theory is relevant to pilot this study based on its assumptions that bother more on humanity, respect and love for one another, collaborativeness and compassionateness. Implementation of love and relatedness among the teachers, student and their administrator bother on adequate communication because communication is the driver of relationships (Koen, 2018). Also, the relevancy of Ubuntu philosophy lies in its recognition and respect for others in the organization which could be equated to participatory decision making which is significant to teachers' productivity (Kolawole, 2016). Above all, through the expression of love and

compassion for the subordinate by the principal makes this theory more relevant to this study. All this has been tested to be a point for teachers' motivation for effectiveness in schools (Aina *et al.*, 2015). However, in schools, teachers need principal, principal needs teachers, students need teachers and teachers need a student to survive and achieve their expected outcomes. Therefore, the idea of Mbhele (2015) that Ubuntu has a role to play in ensuring good leadership for school performance is not irrelevant to the operationalisation of secondary schools in Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

Based on the above background, the study examined the relatedness in the principals' organisational behaviour as correlates of teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State Nigeria. This is done by investigating the likely relationships between organisational communication and teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools. The relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and its effects on teacher effectiveness was also investigated. Furthermore, the study also investigated principals' disposition to the management of stress among teachers and its correlational outcomes on teacher effectiveness in secondary schools. All were done to be able to proffer solutions to the problem of ineffectiveness as observed among teachers. In other to achieve these, the below research questions and hypothesis drives the study to a logical conclusion.

Research Question

In order to understand the level to which the perceived teachers' ineffectiveness has gone to affect the secondary school's productivities in Ekiti State Nigeria, The following question was raised;

- What is the level of teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State?

Research Hypotheses

In other to respond to the correlational effects on the sub-variables of principal behaviour against teachers' effectiveness, the following hypotheses were raised;

1. There is no significant relationship between communication and teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant relationship between principals' management of teachers' stress and teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria

4. Principal behaviour variables will not significantly predict teacher effectiveness.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive system of research with concurrent use of survey design. Descriptive research enables the researcher to describe an existing situation in the field of study (Nassaji, 2015). This made descriptive relevant to the study in order to be able to describe the existing situation as regards the principals' behaviours and its correlational effect on teachers effectiveness. A survey design was used to complement the descriptiveness of the research problem because it covers a wide range of scope. This according to Ominrin (2010) and Jamie-Hale (2018) will make generalization of the findings possible. The population for the study covers all public secondary schools in Ekiti State Nigeria. As at the time of this study, there were 203 public secondary schools (www.ekiti.com). The sample for the study comprises 360 secondary school students and 360 secondary school teachers. These participants were selected using a multi-stage sampling procedure alongside simple random sampling technique at every stage of the procedure.

The first stage involves the selection of local government' areas of the state, among 16 local government from the three senatorial districts. Simple random techniques were used to select nine (9) local governments; three (3) local government areas each from the three senatorial districts. The second stage involved the use of simple random sampling to select four (4) secondary schools each from the Nine (9) local government areas across the three senatorial districts totalling 36 secondary schools. The third stage equally adopted the use of simple random sampling to select ten (10) teachers and ten (10) students from each of the selected 36 secondary schools. The total respondents are 720. The study adopted a self-designed questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaires are tagged Principal Behaviours Questionnaire (PBQ) and Teachers' Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ). The former was administered on teachers while the later was administered on students. PBQ has two sections A and B; section A of PBQ consisted of respondents' background information while section B of PBQ contains 30 items/questions addressing the indices of principals' behaviours which is limited to Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). QTE equally design with two sections; A and B, Section A of QTE is also the background information of the respondents while section

B comprises of 20 Items/questions measuring teacher effectiveness. The answer to these is limited to Highly Effective (HE), Effective (E), Less Effective (LE) and Not Effective (NE).

The instruments were subjected to face and content validity to ensure that the instrument measures its intended targets. Likewise, the test-retest method of reliability was done to ensure the consistent level of the instruments (Omodan & Tsotetsi, 2018). The reliability co-efficient of 0.77 and 0.99 were obtained for PBQ and TEQ respectively. This was adjudged statistically reliable enough. The study used descriptive and inferential statistic to make sense of the data collected. The descriptive statistic such as frequency counts and percentages were used to answer the research question. Alongside, the inferential statistic such as Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Multiple Regression Analysis was adopted to test the above-raised hypothesis. Hypotheses 1, 2, and 3 were tested using PPMC and hypothesis 4 was tested using Multiple Regression Analysis. All of these are null hypotheses and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

This session presents the analysis of data and discussion of findings. Presentation of data was carried out in two stages. The first stage involved the analysis of the research question earlier raised in the study and the second stage covers the testing of hypotheses. Discussions of the findings were presented at the end of the analysis.

Results

The results of the study were reported below by answering the generated research questions and the hypotheses that piloted the study.

Research Question

What is the level of teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State?

In order to answer the question, scores relating to teacher effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State were computed using items 1-20 of "Questionnaire on Teacher effectiveness (QTE)". Respondents who scored less than 50% of the total score on teacher effectiveness were categorized as "Low" level of teacher effectiveness while those whose scores ranged between 50-69 percent and 70 percent and above were classified into "moderate" and "high" levels of teacher effectiveness. The result is presented in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1: Level of teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State

Level of trade unions' activities	Frequency	Percentage
Low (0.00–49.99)	41	11.4
Moderate (50.00–69.99)	241	66.9
High (70.00–100.00)	78	21.7
Total	360	100.0

The above table is further represented graphically as follow;

Table 1 and figure 1 presents the level of teacher effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State. The result shows that out of 360 respondents sampled, 41 representing 11.4 percent had a low level. Those who had moderate level were 241 representing 66.9 percent while those with high level were 78 representing 21.7 percent. Therefore, the level of teacher effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State is moderate. The implication is that the level of teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State is on an average level which is not healthy enough for school productivity.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: *There is no significant relationship between communication and teachers' effectiveness.*

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to communication and teacher effectiveness were computed and subjected to statistical analysis involving Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Communication and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r _{cal}	r _{table}	Remark
Communication	360	8.94	3.53	0.532*	.001	Significant
Teacher effectiveness	360	54.06	18.07			

*p<0.05

Table 2 shows that there is a significant relationship between communication and teacher effectiveness at 0.05 level of significance ($r=0.532$, $p<0.05$). The hypothesis is rejected. The relationship between communication and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ekiti State is high and statistically significant in a positive direction.

Hypothesis 2: *There is no significant relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and teachers' effectiveness.*

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to teachers' participation in decision making and teacher effectiveness were computed and subjected to statistical analysis involving Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 7.

Table 3: Teachers' participation in decision making and teachers' effectiveness

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r _{cal}	r _{table}	Remark
Teachers' participation in decision making	360	8.52	3.948	0.556*	.001	Significant
Teacher effectiveness	360	54.06	18.066			

*p<0.05

Table 3 shows that there is a significant relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ekiti State at 0.05 level of significance ($r=0.556$, $p<0.05$). The relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ekiti State is significant in a positive direction.

Hypothesis 3: *There is no significant relationship between principals' management of stress and teachers' effectiveness.*

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to principals' management of stress and teacher effectiveness were computed and subjected to statistical analysis involving Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Principals' management of stress and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r _{cal}	r _{table}	Remark
Principals' management of stress	360	9.19	3.11	0.489*	.001	Significant
Teacher effectiveness	360	54.06	18.07			

*p<0.05

Table 4 indicates that there is a significant relationship between principals' management of stress and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ekiti State at 0.05 level of significance ($r=0.489, p<0.05$). The null hypothesis is rejected. The relationship between principals' management of stress and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ekiti State is moderate and significant in a positive direction.

Hypothesis 4: Principal behaviour variables will not significantly predict teachers' effectiveness.

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to principal behaviour variables and teacher effectiveness were computed using item 1 – 30 in “Principal Behaviour Questionnaire (PBQ)” and 1- 20 in ‘ Questionnaire on Teacher Effectiveness (QTE)’. These scores were subsequently subjected to statistical analysis involving Multiple Regression Analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The result is shown in Table 5.

Table 1: Principal's behaviour variables and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	P
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	26.797	2.535		10.572	.000
Communication	.862	.421	.170	2.048	.041
Participation in decision making	1.389	.396	.305	3.503	.001
Principal's management of stress	.834	.379	.144	2.202	.028

Multiple R = 0.573, Multiple R²=0.329, Adjusted Multiple R²= 0.323, F_{3,356}=58.127

*p<0.05

Table 1 shows that principal behaviour variables significantly predicted teacher effectiveness ($F_{3,356}=58.127^*$, $p<0.05$). The null hypothesis was rejected. There was significant

positive multiple correlation between the predictor variables (communication, participation in decision making and principal's management of organizational stress) and **teachers'** effectiveness ($R=0.573$, $p<0.05$). This implies that all the predictor variables are factors that can exert influence on teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The value of the coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.329$) indicated that all the predictor variables jointly accounted for 32.9% ($R^2 \times 100$) of the observed variance in teachers effectiveness while the remaining 67.1% unexplained variance could be attributed to variation in other variables outside the regression model. The result further reveals that the single best predictor of teachers' effectiveness is communication ($\beta = 0.421$), closely followed by participation in decision making ($\beta = 0.396$) while principal's management of stress ($\beta = 0.379$) was the least in terms of contribution to teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools. The calculated F-ratio (32.849) was statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the predictor variables jointly provided a significant explanation for the variation in the teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools. The regression equation is given as:

$$Y = 26.797 + 0.862X_1 + 1.389X_2 + 0.834X_3$$

Where

- X_1 = Communication
- X_2 = Participation in decision making
- X_3 = Principal's management of organizational stress
- b_i = ($i=1-3$) Regression Weight Coefficients
- a = Constant (other variables other than X_1-X_3)

Findings and Discussion

The answer to the research question showed that the level of teacher effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State is moderate. It can, therefore, be implied that teachers' activities towards work in terms of teachers' classroom management, lesson preparation, interpersonal relationship with other staff, mastery of subject matter and instructional delivery is on average priority by the teachers. This kind of result is not healthy enough to bring about teacher's productivity in secondary school. Because the reality as deduced from the result has confirmed the unhealthy teacher's effectiveness in the school. This is in line with findings confirming that teachers are operating under the influence of low morale and motivation to work (Kavita & Hassan, 2018; Ukonu, Serieke-Dickson & Edeoga, 2019). This scenario shows that the philosophy of

Ubuntu is practically absent among the teachers and their principals who may have resulted into individualistic operation as against humanism and togetherness preached by the principle of Ubuntu (Mbhele, 2015).

The findings from hypothesis 1 showed that there was a significant relationship between communication and teacher effectiveness. It implies that the principals' communication with the teachers is relevant to teachers' effectiveness, that is when there is good communication system between the principal and the teachers will enhance the activities of teacher for better productivities, therefore, must be given needful attention. This finding supports the studies of Holtzhausen (2002) and Goris (2007) that effective communication improves job satisfaction and job performance which in turn improves staff effectiveness and productivity. In the same vein, the findings of Gray, (2013) and Rai (2018) also corroborate our findings by linking teachers' effectiveness to effective communication of school managers. This according to Rai (2018) increases teachers' morale to work and also reduce misunderstanding and interpersonal conflict among staff. This is further confirmed that the principal's role in managing teachers in schools lies in good professional and personal relationships which could only be ensured through good communication system (Weber & Scott, 2013). With this, it is practical evidence that Ubuntu philosophy if practice in schools will further enhance interconnectedness between teachers and principal, which is a pointer to positive behaviours (Msila, 2008).

The findings from hypothesis 2 revealed that there is a significant relationship between teachers' participation in decision making and teacher effectiveness. This shows that teacher effectiveness will be enhanced if they are fully involved in decision-making processes. That is, the school's principal should at all-time recognise the importance of teachers by ensuring their involvement in the decision-making process of the school. This will further implement the assumptions of Ubuntu philosophy that people exist because there are people, meaning, a person is a person through others (Moloketi, 2009; Khomba, 2011) This is found to have contributed to the management of disparities in the workplace (Nzimakwe, 2014). This finding according to literature is significant to teachers' motivation (Uchendu, et al. (2013). This is also in agreement with findings which indicate a strong association between teachers' involvement in decision making, organisational commitment, high productivity and job effectiveness (Uchendu, et al., 2013; Fakunle, 2016; Balogun, 2017).

Furthermore, the findings from hypothesis 3 showed that there was a significant relationship between principals' management of stress and teacher effectiveness. There confirmed the fact that that the employees' effectiveness depends largely on the stress management strategies that are put in place, most especially by educational institutions. To this end, teacher effectiveness will be enhanced, where the stress management mechanisms are in place. The finding is quietly close to the outcome of the study of Gillespie, Walsh, Winefield, Dua & Stough (2001) that stress hampers the normal routine of teachers by negatively affecting their performance at work. In the same vain, the findings of Kavita & Hassan (2018) and Ukonu, Serieke-Dickson & Edeoga (2019) is in agreement with our findings that teachers stress was a major contributor to teachers' effectiveness in schools. This is also confirming the conclusion of Pagayanan (2016) that environmental pressures, the pressure to produce better exam results, the pressure to perform extraneous tasks, and extreme classroom ecology in the Philippines has greatly affected the performance of secondary schools teachers. However, the situation in Ekiti State Nigeria is not in exception. The space of Ubuntu here is that humanity towards others, social respect and responsibilities for ethical attitude towards others is essential (Lefa, 2015).

Lastly, finding from regression analysis, hypothesis 4, showed that there were significant positive multiple correlations between the predictor variables which are communication, participation in decision making and principal's management of organizational stress and teachers' effectiveness. The result further showed that communication among other variables is the best predictor of teachers' effectiveness. This implies that communication is only important in the school's system but also contribute significantly to the effectiveness of teachers for better productivity. As discussed earlier the theoretical frameworks, communication brings about good relationship which Ubuntu philosophy is at the forefront of organizational effectiveness. That is, social and interpersonal relationships are needed to maintain effectiveness in the school system (Msengana, 2006).

Conclusion and Implication for Practice

Inference from this study indicates that a good communication system in secondary schools is one of the important factors that are responsible for general productivity. Meaning that teachers and probably all other stakeholders cherish good communication between the principal to the teachers, teachers to principals, students to the principal and their teachers. By so doing, they feel carried along and thereby see themselves as an important capital needed to ensure good

productivity. Also, the allowance of teachers' participation and or involvement in decisions making the process as found to be significant to teachers' effectiveness is also a determinant to the achievement of schools goals and objective. Not only that, the policy frameworks for curriculum implementation in Nigeria schools (FGN, 2013) can only be achieved in a schools environment where all the stakeholders work mutually with one mind and for one goal. This according to Ubuntu philosophy promotes humanity, togetherness and recognition (April & Peters, 2011; Ronnie, 2018). Hence, this conclusion will be better made by lining stress management to teachers' well-being which is translating to teachers' effectiveness. That is, stress-free teachers, become an object of productivity.

Therefore, communication, participatory decision making and principal management of stress are the dimensions of teachers' effectiveness and general productivity in secondary schools with a preferable emphasis on good organizational communication as the major determinant of teachers' effectiveness. Based on the above, the following recommendations are made to improve practices in secondary schools;

1. The secondary school managers such as principal and other supporting managers should design a workable, implementable and conducive communication mechanism that will accommodate feedback from teachers and other stakeholders. This will make teachers' feel recognised and important in the management of the school. When this is done, the implementation of the school's curriculum will be done by the teachers without huddles and thereby enhance teacher effectiveness.
2. The secondary school administrators such as principal should make it a point of necessity to carry teachers along by involving them in the decision making process. Most especially on the issue that directly or indirectly concerns them and their job and in all matters that concerns the school development, through the operation of the open-door policy in the administration of the schools. This will go a long way to improve teacher effectiveness.
3. Since principals' dispositions to teachers welfare such as stress management are responsible for teachers' effectiveness. Therefore, it becomes expedient for schools administrators such as principals and other managers to ensure that whatever work situation/stressor that can bring about job retrogression in the life of the teachers are adequately and approximately handled. This will aid teachers' effectiveness because the teachers possibly to see their principal as being compassionate and humane. This according

to Ubuntu philosophy is a way of life that motivate for effectiveness leading to productivity.

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